

A 2.45GHz SiGe Power Amplifier with a Novel Digital Predistortion using Orthogonal Sequences

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Abstract—With the need of maximizing the efficiency of Radio Frequency (RF) systems while respecting strict constraints in terms of EVM requirements, Power Amplifiers (PAs) predistortion appears as a way to improve circuits performances. Indeed, maximum efficiency is near the maximum output power that the PA can display. However, in this use area, PAs introduce distortion and phase variation. In this paper, a novel method for the linearization of RF Power Amplifiers is presented. The sequential transform is first used to evaluate a digital model of predistortion for the PA. A AB-Class PA is designed and is used in the proposed predistortion system to highlight the benefits of the overall architecture.

Keywords—Digital predistortion, Sequential Transform, Power Amplifier, SiGe Power Amplifier

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to meet the exponential growth of communications, different types of digital modulation are used such as Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) or Wideband Code Division Multiple Access (WCDMA). These techniques allow for increasing the spectral efficiency of data exchanges. However, the increase in spectral efficiency is linked to a high Peak-to-Average-Power Ratio (PAPR) which is a challenge for the Power Amplifier (PA) design. Indeed, linear PAs have poor efficiency over the linear zone and will considerably reduce the overall system efficiency [1]. On the other side, modulations like OFDM are very sensitive to non-linearities that can be introduced by high-efficiency PAs. Non-linearities modify the amplitude and phase of the input signal and lead to the creation of undesired intermodulations products (IMD) in adjacent communication channels as shown in Fig. 1.

A way to answer both power efficiency and reducing intermodulation products issues is to use the PA near the maximum efficiency area and predistortion methods to reduce IMD. Digital Predistortion (DPD) [2] is a widely used technique. It consists in compensating the distortion of the PA while working in the high-efficiency non-linear area. In DPD, an inverse model of the PA called predistorter (PD) needs to be introduced ahead of the PA. The complete system will then behave like a linear system. However, PAs are time-variant systems. Temperature, drift, and memory effects may change the equivalent model of the PA [3] and an update is then necessary to have an equivalent inverse model of the PA anytime.

This paper presents a new approach to identify the predistorter by replacing the temporal base with a sequential

Fig. 1. Normalized Power Spectral Density (PSD) of input and output signals of a non-linear PA.

base. It increases the convergence speed of the least-squares method (LMS) and also the speed of the system and the efficiency. Section II presents the mathematical model of the proposed algorithm. Finally, experimental validation is done. A AB-class PA is designed based on a BFP780 SiGe Transistor from Infineon and used in a predistortion system to perform modulated signal measurements with and without the predistortion algorithm.

II. DIGITAL PREDISTORTION IN A SEQUENTIAL BASE

In order to identify a predistorter model of the PA, an adaptive filtering or least squares method [4] is used. The most common mathematical model used to determine the pair PA/PD is the memory polynomial (MP):

$$y_t[n] = \mathbf{u}[n]\mathbf{h}[n] \quad (1)$$

With :

- Q non-linearity degree, M memory depth.
- $\mathbf{h}[n] = [h_{10}, h_{20}, \dots, h_{Q0}, h_{11}, \dots, h_{Q1}, \dots, h_{QM}]^T$ coefficients of the MP model.
- $\mathbf{u}[n] = [x[n], x^2[n], \dots, x^Q[n], x[n-1], \dots, x^Q[n-M-1]]$ the input vector in the MP base.
- $y_t[n]$ output signal of the model.

The adaptive behavior of the algorithm depends on the eigenvalues of the autocorrelation matrix of the input signal on the chosen basis :

$$\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{u}} = E[\mathbf{u}[n]\mathbf{u}[n]^T] \quad (2)$$

The smaller the gap between the eigenvalues, the better the convergence dynamics. An efficient way to reduce this gap is to transpose the LMS algorithm on another computational basis via an orthogonal transform. The Discrete Sequential Transform (DST) is a mathematical tool allowing to switch from temporal adaptive filtering to sequential adaptive filtering (SLMS). Similar to the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), it describes any signal \mathbf{x} in a base consisting of N orthogonal sequences \mathbf{W} .

$$X[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n]W_L[k, n] \quad (3)$$

On a vectorized form:

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}\mathbf{W}_L \quad (4)$$

With :

- $X[k]$ is the k^{e} sequential coefficient for $k \in [0, 1, \dots, N-1]$.
- $x[n]$ is the n^{e} sample of $x(t)$ sampling on 2^N points.
- L is the order of the transform ($L = \log_2(N)$), N being a power of 2.
- $W_L[k, n]$ is the value k^{e} row and n^{e} column of the sequential matrix \mathbf{W}_L with discrete sequential sequences.

The proposed block diagram of the sequential LMS algorithm is presented in Fig. 2. The purpose of the SLMS algorithm is to estimate the sequential coefficient \mathbf{H} (equivalent to the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) of h) to minimize the sequential mean square error (MSE). Instead of processing the signal sample by sample, they are accumulated in buffers of size N to perform a N -DWT. The DWT for a different power of x can be obtained thanks to the following properties :

$$\mathbf{X} \circledast \mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{y} \mathbf{W}_L \quad (5)$$

\circledast is the logical convolution operator and \cdot the term-to-term multiplication. By recursion, it is possible to obtain the memory polynomials on a sequential basis :

$$\mathbf{X}_2 = \mathbf{X} \circledast \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}^2 \mathbf{W}_L \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{X}_q = \mathbf{X}_{q-1} \circledast \mathbf{X} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the proposed sequential LMS algorithm.

The equations use to obtain the sequential model of the system are similar to the temporal equations. The algorithm converges with a speed equivalent to that of an Recursive Least Squares algorithm with less complexity ($O(n \log(n))$) instead of ($O(n^2)$).

The original algorithm developed to realize a digital predistortion is presented in this Section. The purpose of the next Section is to present the AB-Class PA that will be used for the demonstration.

III. DESIGNED OF SiGe AB-CLASS POWER AMPLIFIER

A. AB-Class Power Amplifier bias

In order to evaluate the complete predistortion chain as shown in Fig. 2, a AB-Class PA is designed on Advanced Design Systems (ADS) from Keysight. The chosen structure is a one-stage common emitter with a BFP780 SiGe transistor from Infineon and the substrate used for electromagnetic (EM) simulations and manufacture is Rogers 4003C ($\epsilon_r = 3.38$).

The targeted requirements for the proposed PA are: a center frequency $f_c = 2.45\text{GHz}$, an output saturation power of 17 dBm at the center frequency, and a maximum Power-Added Efficiency (PAE) of more than 25%.

The schematic of the proposed PA is shown in Fig. 3. Supposing a AB class operation and with an imposed collector voltage of $V_c = 5\text{V}$, the chosen base voltage is equal to $V_b = 0.8\text{V}$. These DC voltages are brought to the transistor's base and collector thanks to $\frac{\lambda}{4}$ transmission lines acting as RF choke inductors. Length of these two $\frac{\lambda}{4}$ transmission lines is equal to $L_{\frac{\lambda}{4}} = \frac{c}{f\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} = 19\text{mm}$ calculated at $f = 2.45\text{GHz}$. Lastly, two resistors are placed at the emitter of the transistor, in order to prevent thermal runaway of the transistor when the PA is working at high input power.

B. Input and output matching networks

Resonant stubs are used instead of lumped elements to realize input and output matching networks.

The 3D view and dimensions of both stubs are shown in Fig. 4. Input impedance seen for the PA is $Z_{in} = 8.5 + j*22.45\ \Omega$ whereas the optimal conjugate output impedance is $Z_{opt} = 10.5 + j*5\ \Omega$. Both impedances are evaluated at $f = 2.45\text{GHz}$.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the proposed AB-Class SiGe Power Amplifier.

Fig. 4. 3D view and sizing of input and output matching resonant stubs.

The chosen topology is an open stub with a microstrip transmission line using a ground plane at the bottom face of the circuit.

C. Simulation results

After having designed the necessary components for the PA, the layout of the circuit is done. This layout is simulated on ADS electromagnetic simulator: Momentum. The purpose is to obtain the post-layout simulations (PLS) before manufacturing the circuit.

Small signal (S parameters) and large signal parameters are presented in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. The 3 dB bandwidth seen on S_{21} is from 2 GHz to 2.6 GHz with a $S_{21max} = 13.9$ dB at $f = 2.45$ GHz. S_{11} obtained is below -10 dB between 2.4 GHz and 2.455 GHz and small signal output matching S_{22} below -10 dB between 1.6 GHz and 2.55 GHz.

Harmonic balance simulations are running at $f = 2.45$ GHz. Power gain at $f = 2.45$ GHz is 11 dB where the saturation output power is 18 dBm. The output compression point of the PA is 17 dBm for an input power of 7 dBm. This area will be the area of interest for predistortion measurements in order to linearize the PA at input power level close to the maximum efficiency of 29%.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

After verifying the small and large signal behavior of the PA with PLS simulations, the results obtained comply with the

Fig. 5. S parameters obtain for PLS simulations.

Fig. 6. Large signal results from PLS simulations.

targeted specifications. The circuit is manufactured in order to be measured and proposed as a demonstration of the complete test bench. The layout view and manufactured circuit are shown in Fig. 7.

A. Continuous wave measurements

Continuous wave (CW) simulations and measurements are first performed. A comparison between simulations and measurements is shown in Fig. 8.

Large signal parameters are in good agreement between simulations and measurements with a measured maximum power gain equals to 10.5 dB and an output compression point $OCP_{1dB} = 17$ dBm. The compression area of the PA is identified for input power above 7 dBm. In order to highlight the benefits of the predistortion algorithm seen in Section II, modulated signal measurements are carried out using an OFDM modulation around this input power area.

B. Modulated signal measurements

After having characterized the PA in CW, modulated signal measurements are performed. The input modulated signal,

Fig. 7. Layout view and manufactured circuit of the proposed Power Amplifier.

Fig. 8. Comparison simulations vs measurements for large signal parameters at $f = 2.45\text{GHz}$.

use for the demonstration, is a 64-QAM OFDM with 5 MHz bandwidth and 1 dBm of average power. The center frequency is 2.45 GHz with a Peak-to-Average-Power Ratio (PAPR) of 9.8 dB. This signal is generated using a USRP B210. MATLAB is running the proposed digital predistortion algorithm presented in Section II. The non-linearity coefficient is $Q = 3$ and the memory depth is $M = 2$.

The measurement test bench described previously is shown in Fig. 9. The output signal of the PA is measured on a spectrum analyzer, extracted, and sent to MATLAB.

Fig. 10 shows the output spectrum obtained with and without the predistortion algorithm. Adjacent Channel to Power Ratio (ACPR) is measured for the upper and lower band around the center frequency. On the lower band, the ACPR increased from -33 dBc to -42.3 dBc with the predistortion algorithm, and on the upper band, the ACPR increased from -31.9 dBc to -42.9 dBc. The overall gain on ACPR is 9 to 11 dB for both bands. The linearity improvement obtained thanks to this method can achieve linearity requirements for 5G communication standards.

The ACPR improvement obtained with the proposed demonstrator is similar to what is seen on DPD made on integrated circuits (IC) on the same frequency band. These results confirm the demonstrator's behavior made with compo-

Fig. 9. Sequential DPD test bench.

Fig. 10. Output spectrum for an OFDM input signal with (blue) and without (red) digital predistortion.

TABLE I
COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART

Reference	[5]	[6]	[7]	<i>This work</i>
Freq. [GHz]	5.44	1.92	1	2.45
Modulation	OFDM	WCDMA	OFDM	OFDM
BW [MHz]	20	5	5	5
P_{out} [dBm]	8	15.8	23	10
ACPR impr. [dB]	7	12	10	11
Type of circuit	IC	IC	IC	COTS

nents-of-the-shelf (COTS). The next step will be to apply this technique on a PA integrated into a 28nm FDSOI technology, associated with the DPD operation.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel digital predistortion using orthogonal sequences. The convergence speed of this algorithm is remarkable, allowing for results to be obtained in a shorter time and with less complexity compared to more traditional approaches. A SiGe AB-Class PA is designed and used in the complete predistortion system. Linearity enhancement is highlighted by modulated signal measurements with and without the proposed predistortion algorithm. An ACPR enhancement of 11 dB on the upper band has been shown on modulated signal measurements which can lead to linearity enhancement for PA dedicated to 5G standards. The further step is to evaluate this predistortion algorithm applied to an integrated PA and on upper-frequency bands for 6G applications.

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